

CAUSES AND PREVENTIONS OF HATE CRIMES IN MODERN AGE, A
CONTEXTUAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This article looks at hate crimes from three main areas specifically sociology, psychology, and economics for the sake of to understand the many reasons behind such violence. Looking at society, hate crimes often come from things like unfair treatment, differences between groups, and fights between groups. People in power might try to keep their position by pushing down others. The way people learn from a young age, what they see in the media, and what leaders say can make prejudice seem normal and even acceptable, especially towards groups that are already treated badly. On the mental side, some people are more likely to act in harmful ways because of traits like being strict, not being open to new ideas, or acting out anger in the wrong way. When people feel their way of life or their money is under threat, they might blame others for their problems. Also, seeing other groups as less than human can make it easier to hurt them. Money and jobs also matter a lot. When the economy is struggling, with people worried about their jobs and not having enough resources, hate crimes can go up. People might start to blame outsiders or certain groups for their problems. Politicians or the media might use these fears to take attention away from real issues and make people target those they see as different. By looking at all these factors together, the article shows how unfair systems, personal attitudes, and financial issues all play a role in creating hate crimes. To stop hate, we need more than just laws. We also need to fix unfair conditions, change how we think about money and work, and teach people to be more understanding and accepting.

INTRODUCTION

Hate crime a term which used through contexts, disciplines and jurisdictions, although there is no unique way to understand the term. The legislators, scholars and policy makers for some reasons be able to discuss it and can practice its silos. For some of the philosophers that "hate Crime" is the occurrence of a

phenomena which reached to the range of aggressions and establishes to marginal groups usually, and what is the range of law which is consider the act of crime. It may be micro-aggressions, discrimination and hate speech. As per other researchers, the term "hate crime" is the only context of criminal act which is a

narrow in construction. Moreover, Garland and Chakraborti described the term “as having operational and conceptual ambiguity with somewhat elusive and slippery notion raising thorny questions” for them who has been accused with responding with it (Schweppe1, 2021). Here is a legal definition of hate crime which has concisely set out in the operation and legal way. It has been known throughout the Scotland, England and wales. Looking before to the motivations and causes of hate crime closely to its dynamics and nature which motivated to victimization which includes the hate crimes and incidents (Human rights, 2016). The number of complexities were highlighted while dealing and defining hate crime, the experts are able to make a decision about and incident that whether it recorded as hate incident or hate crime. It depends on the act of offenders their level of prejudice and can be different in other context. It can be having a strong pivotal relation between committer and biased behavior regarding the crime the commit. It also to noted that sometime the committer biased toward hate crime and do it with determinations as in example to transgender, religion, race and sexual orientation.

The national definition in Northern Ireland, Wales and England for hate crime for the first time coined in 2007 by the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS) and Association of Chief Police Officer (ASPO). This definition provided base for the committer who committed hostility against the known people and determining them who are victimized. The member do not belong to the same group in the enclosure and broad definition. In other words, it can be said that anyone can become victim of hate crime. According to this definition, the CPS and police collected data regarding various categories of hate crimes which are as follows (Roberts et al 2013):

- i. Transgender
- ii. Religion or belief
- iii. Race
- iv. Disability
- v. Sexual orientation

In Britain the term hate crime is used in the criminal justice and in media widely. Although the term is not obvious what it actually means. Specifically, there are various opinions that it is emotional ‘hate’ condenses, and what the situation in which hate can be said as criminal offence, and to whom be protected from it.

In some of the debates it has been clear the term ‘hate’ used in large amount of a contradiction. The victim does not need the hate of hatred who commits hate crime. It can be her or his manifestation of prejudgment or bias toward the victim and the crime more properly characterized (Hall, 2013).

In April 2009 it has been monitored that in last the crime/hate against transgender may added. Resultantly, in April 2010 the meaningful analysis has been monitored hate crime and it’s all kinds. In official record there is a difference between hate crimes and hate incidents which made in routine, and reported or recorded by the National Crime Recording Standards. There are two main components in hate crime. First one is to involve the violation of criminal law, while second one is recognition of the five mentioned categories of crime which associated with aggravating factor. When the component reached to its peak the criminal justice proceed and it attract the court to impose the rigorous sentences. In simple definition the acts which are categorized in hate crimes and refined and changed into various pieces before the court of justice. The amendments made in the act of security 2001 and anti-terrorism crime. As the previous legislation created various religious offences and impose the sentencing which were the same to all other offences and there were proofs of religious exacerbation. Moreover, it has been amended in the Protection of Freedoms Act 2012, which showed newly specified crimes of racially, stalking and religiously committed forms of crimes (Roberts. et.al.2013).

Hate Crime concept

The concept of hate crime for the first time coined in the year of 1970 in United States and obtained more importance since last ten years in UK. Notwithstanding raising of the policy interest and growing academic, it originates more research case in the United States. It has the significant new burning issue around the world and contributing to literature that has been started from Canada, South Africa and Australia. The literature of hate crime has developed in many disciplinary orientations. The important and notable impact originating with different perspectives what has broadly assigned to it e.g. Criminological, social-psychological, psychological and sociological (Iganski, 2008). Apart from this, the knowledgeable

descents tracing the importance finely generate various questions to the researcher to ask and the explanations needs interpretations what they offer. For instance, the individual have more focused by psychologist, small groups of dynamics by social psychologists, social force focused by sociologists and illegal acts by criminologists. Definite ideas and concepts were disaggregating which are organized is as an important roots. Specifically, the sense of hate crime may be beneficial for those who have been treated limited in isolation or give some special interest issue, which were connected to the mainstream traditions. For instance, while examining the available literature, getting understanding to the origin and nature of dogmatic violence which is based on discrimination, racism and disenchanted through extant of prejudice (Green, McFalls and Smith, 2001). The extraordinary research literature review on prejudice can be better to read to know about hate crime. This research study systematically and directly examines that why bias leads to violence. This concept presented by Ardley (2005) stated that “the minute experimental data or examination of explicitly the acts which were targeted in the United Kingdom”. Smith’s, Green and McFalls (2001) reviewed the available literature to found a number of problems, figure out the theoretical synthesis that why hate crimes committed by people and attempt to take it in account.

Patterns of hate crime

Various research studies reviews report showed that hate crimes be able to sometimes create part of the process of victimization which make the experience of victim’s in everyday life due to bias. Some substantial incidents which has been persistent to build up the targeted aggression. It has been emphasized that the committers commit the crime in which they know about the victim and it have proportion of hate crimes. The situation and motivational features which make complex decisions regarding the incidents to present before the court of justice. To respond to hate crime to help the committers in which they set shared sorts incidents that happen in the communities has been highlighted, which have some situational and typical characteristics, i.e. victim- and the committer have relationship and different level of prejudice and various links with each other in these types.

The analysts, scholars and policy makers may have pretenses distinctive difficulty. According to further appearances of criminality, the characteristically common agreement across policy maker and academy and what to concept mean. In the legal definition which the law given to crimes like a rape constitutes, all the definitional boundaries are agreed that what the context means across the world. For various scholars in various jurisdictions and disciplines accept to allow the problematize and explore the context and the analyst and policy makers to understand the occurrence through the jurisdictionally. This comparison have been based on the data and the understandings of jurisdictions that how to remove this social evil from the society (Schweppe, 2021).

When the acts of the committer reach to the criminal verge, the gestures, symbols, words used by the committer has been referring to minimum aggression in the literature, and in practice “hate incidents”. According to Nadal micro aggressions “humiliation of environmental or behavioral, and commonplace verbal, either intentional or unintentional from which members of society are called as hostile, insults and negative slights and create trouble for members of the society” (Nadal & Mendoza, 2014). Sue et al classified three types of micro aggression: i.e. the behavior or unfair language or purposely harsh, micro insults: i.e. the same actions which is committed accidentally, further micro individualizations: i.e. the questioning or trivializations where the lived experiences committed by the members for mineralization (wine Sie et. Al., 2008). The occurrence of micro aggressions be able to relevant in the legal perspective: although the purpose of criminal Law to harm the amount of occurrence, the workplace occurrence, provision of services and goods context, e.g. the acts of equality will lead to reduce the micro aggression (Jan, 2019).

Whatever, important vitally is to understand the context that with a lawful viewpoint, speech of hate and hate crime two different perceptions and made distinctively. Certainly, the offences through hate speech have a vital constitutional pedigree, looking back to the date “the constitution of civil rights and the 20th century creating stat rules, the main objective to the white supremacist actions (Phillips & Grattet, 2000)”. Likewise, in the act of British Race Relations 1966 that racial hatred has been criminalized and the same has been done by the Irish act of Prohibition of

Incitement to Hatred Act 1989. The scholar perceived that the main difference amongst hate crime and hate speech is what a person classified to as the “audience of the crime” the victim is not included in it, nonetheless it may be a distinct audience who be able to stimulated up, and hate speech be able to understand the amount then should be criminalized, and it may be the important argumentative problem in the arena of hate crime (Goodall, 2010).

In Northern Ireland, wales and England, the hate crime is defined as the informed racist offence deriving Stephen Lawrence report of murder by MacPherson (1999). A definition of victim concerned with, the incident which take away the police will to resolve that the incident was committed by motivated or informed prejudice. In wales and England the example of the ACPO the hate incident has defined as non-crime incident “the incident which is apparent to any person or the victim” that the act is motivated by antagonism or bias grounded on the membership of person’s real or perceived in the specific group (ACPO, College of Policing, 2014). The Northern Ireland Police Service defined the hate incident as “the perceived incident which has been committed against a property or on the grounds of personal political opinion or specific disability, sexual orientation, ethnicity, religion and gender identity” (McVeigh, 2017). Furthermore, the PSNI (The Police Service of Northern Ireland) define in the broader context as the legislative process of Northern Ireland. The definition of PSNI and ACPO has different from each other. Whilst the notion of examination used in both. In the definition of PSNI the specified group from which data have been gathered. The legislation of the criminal justice have been outlined in broader sense for these groups (Northern Ireland) Order 2004, spreading to, the definition to include the gender identity and political opinion, agreeing to record the hate crime as transphobic and sectarian. In police services it occurs most frequently, for recording of hate incident by individual the police need legislation of wider categories; in Nottingham, if a hate crime misogyny record by the police on the basis of this definition “misogyny hate crime” being “the incidents what happened against women on the basis of motivated behavior of men toward women and target the women simply due to that they are women

(Mullany & Trickett, 2018, BBC berk; Mason-Bish, 2016,).

Who commits hate crimes?

The overview presented that who commit hate crimes in UK? According to Bennett’s, Levin and McDevitt (2002) identified the four wide types of hate crime offenders:

- i. Offender of thrill: these are those committers who do crimes for excitement or thrill
- ii. Offender of defensive: those who commit crimes as defend themselves
- iii. Offenders of mission: these committers whose mission in life is to free the world from the group of evil doer and inferior
- iv. Offenders of Retaliatory: these are engaged with revengeful violence of the belief and do it so, just desserts is served (McDevitt et al, 2002)

The study of Bennett’s, McDevitt and Levin was limited a police cases through secondary analysis in Bostan, USA. The young offenders were did not interviewed by the police, who commit crime in gangs to attack on ethnic groups and gays in outside in their areas, that why get the thrill and excitement through this way? As per Garland and Chakroborti (2009) highlighted that “the youths are seeking thrill or excitement over these assault, they depicted that the presence of stereotypes and negative attitude regarding marginalized people that the pain they got is meaningless”. The impact, responses and causes of hate crime. “Offenders for defense, in Bennett’s, Levin and McDevitt (2002) study revealed that the assault on those who are in ethnic minorities whenever they go to the areas of white people. It is beneficial to clarify through categories that the committer of hate crime does not belong to the single same group. The fact is, that group 1, 2 and 4 are the more wide range violent groups. To see the details of the offenders of hate crime, Iganski and Smith (2011) argued that most of the young males have a tendency to ‘versatile’ in committing hate crime and they involved in most of the other kinds crime. Moreover, the so called “thrill offenders, the attacker on gays McDevitt’s and Levin study, highlighted that normally “average” of the young offenders have criminal record in hate crimes. The increasing flow of prejudice and bloodshed, the Smith and Iganski were not clear on as either the offenders, who perpetuate hate crimes, have

a tendency to concentration on one type of victim or target the people of wide range who are dissimilar to defend themselves. As Schafer (2002) stated that most of the perpetrators have faith in that their struggles involving to make a diverse society. As Perry (2001) highlighted, that it is a technique of power and oppression, which are done intently to confirm the hierarchies and given characteristics to social order. This biasness motivate perpetrators to create their domination simultaneously and oppress the victim's identity. The offenders use criminal acts, that may be hate speech and hate campaigns, as it is process to enhance their thrilling ideas whose beliefs that might they agree with them or instill fear among them. The range of individuals of hate crime is high, they sometime attacks physically in the streets on other person due to their affiliation with others who belong to hate group and this is an initiative to send message to the larger community. The people who committed hate crimes are mostly like co-offenders, it means they did not like other methods of crimes, their acts frequently occur in multiple criminals (Lantz & Kim 2019). Their motives are often mostly for the result more serious injury or harm. these various kinds of offenses, and this may be because of co-offenders. Similarly, the offenders who like multiple offenses increased their crimes and they don't have any relationship with victims and do the crimes of public pleasures (Pezzella & Fetzer, 2017). The subset of youngster who commit hate crime target their victims on the basis of gender identity or sexual orientation. The age of the offenders are almost 24 years, they most likely commits crimes to kill or injuring their victims. Other kinds of offenders who had highest rates. Most of the crime offenders target their victims on the basis or nationality, race or ethnicity. While their ages are median of 26 years, the racial and ethnic discrimination motivated offenders to commit hate crimes because of their involvement in hate groups or low education achievements. It has been observed that the offenders who select targets through religious characteristics had military service and mental illness. Offenders were almost an older or average age of the targets, they were married and having children but commit their hate crimes due to their superiority. The individuals who became the victims are mostly on the basis of religion. The offenders commit crimes like

property damage just like as synagogues and mosques (Jensen et al, 2020; Jan, 2025).

Causes of hate crimes

The above are various types of hate crimes and there are many causes of it. The following is an overview many factors which has been considered to explain that why people commit hate crimes. There are various persuasive argument liking attitudes, perceptions of threat and hate crimes and structural factors of hate crimes. There are some proofs which supports theories for explanation of hate crime but the proof which is base for hate crime connection stands weak. This may be the result of lack of research area, but the facts that there are various multiple facts and variables which affect human's behaviors. It is to understand and significant to know about different contexts, forms, and hate crime drivers, and knowing about the factors for perpetrations are likely common.

Psychological

Psychological justifications be likely to starts from the perception of someone to individual aggression to victim's social group. These offender limits themselves to the results of their affective and cognitive practices through which offenders specify their targets, create grudges and involve them in violence as well as in aggression. The important and clarifying key words that hate crimes the disproportionate or extreme types of personal biasness (Kleg 1983 and Roberts 1995). Gordon Allport's (1954) stated that stereotyping attached to 'affective disorders' of projection, paranoia, frustration, and guilt avoidance which drives the individual to perpetrate discrimination, avoidance, multiple types of interpersonal violence and hate speech. It is going from the lower level of physical assault, by homicide or even genocide of entire group. There are different approaches on prejudice which limiting the bases of prejudice and unable to answer the questions that why prejudices are obtained and maintained.

Similarly Brown (2011) argues that "Prejudice remain for the reason that individual profits by it", Intricate that hate crimes are characterized by psychological attributes of individuals likely based on prejudice. Mostly whereas the appeals for profiling of personality to policy makers and practitioners to concluded that psychological accounts of individuals remain not

properly diagnosed. They point out a large amount of attitudinal surveys and it has been confirmed that the offenders of hate crimes have authoritarian tendencies, and lesser subsection of authoritarians individual are found to be hate criminal (Green, McFalls and Smith, 2001).

Social Psychological

The social psychological clarification for reasons by offenders of hate crime, is not to recognize the search for the means of possibly violent prejudicial orientations but in sometimes it also be expressed. The dynamics of small group recommend the conformism, contagion, which encourage the extremists beliefs on the affecting people to more dangerous arrogances, embarrassment and the desire for the acceptance of the group, which encourage a person to indulge in hate crime (Bohnisch and winter, 1993). The mass media has also influence on such accounts. Sensational events on hate crimes has resulted as reason to encourage 'spikes' or 'contagion' events in hate crimes (Brosius and Esser 1995). The active role of media in propagating, formulating and the target population by stereotypes legitimately. Similarly, the distribution of political parties and organizations, just like Al-Qaeda and far-right groups, political discourse and hate amplifying. In the study of Blee's (2007), it was find that in the United States, female members were white supremacist/far-right groups. Excitingly, it has been analyzed that thee recruitment and propaganda on internet have great influence in the incensement of hate crimes. In this part of literature specifically 'psychological', looking for the interpretive account that why people and groups are engaged in hate crimes. Conceptual resources has been drawn from psychological studies from various social sciences disciplines like social work, sociology, forensic psychotherapy and counselling. The important excellence of these contributes to the idea of Sociological phenomenon (Class, Gender, Strain, poverty and inequality) and psychological phenomenon (emotions, dispositions and personalities) shall be reduced to each other. This idea leads to various question on social scientific notions, essentially as problematic, on the basis that someone should not take up because they are belonged to the same demographic group, likely feel and think the same. Hate crime offenders have

considering questions regarding their motivations. Gadd and Jefferson (2007) highlighted that hate crime motivations that amalgamation of relational psychoanalytic and post-structuralist perceptions of the individuals who are not conditioned through upbringing or social circumstances, but be able to select in imperfect circumstances to represent themselves. The idea that they may be motivated by out-feelings which they were failed to clear is important in clarifying that why individuals commit hate crimes.

Sociological

There are many and different hate crimes which is based on sociological accounts, while hate crime can be treat as a type of delinquency and youth violence. According to the authors, hate crime is principally resulted as the 'anomic' outbreaks to the poor individuals of the society or it is from cohesion reaction to suppress group or community (Green, McFalls and Smith 2001). As Kathleen Blee's (2007) cited in the research, that the attraction to violence has seemed parse. The offenders for the violence is attached to extremist groups, although the attached to supremacist ideology or particular race. The skinhead group of white power members perceived by her, they always attacked each other violently as ritualized group dynamics. Sometimes members switch and joined anti-fascist groups with their former allies to engage in violent clashes. She concluded that violence creates group, somewhat than being essentially a result of group strategy. Additionally, 'Defended their Community Perspective' that why individual commit hate crime is important sociological contribution (Suttles 1972). It perceives, specifically hate crimes are racial, and tactics for protecting the threats posed against their ways of life and identities. This perception is considered as a variant of traditional racial threat or as Srolovitch, wong and Green (1998) suggested, "a rapprochement within realistic and symbolic perceptions". The hate crimes target not just individual victim but the entire social group symbolically (Boyd, Hamner and Berk, 1996). Similarly, these hate crimes having specifically bad results that resound the communities. These crimes, comparatively minor offences in the criminal law, and may extremely disturb the communities worsening to any pressure and aggregate the cause for revenge thus

rising in crime. Further, these kind of acts are likely probably detained by extremist groups as proof and the extreme political stance (Craig, 1999).

Economic and Political

According to Banton (1983) and Bjorgo (1993) that some of the communities developed the defended themes and have obtained an important grip. Whilst, the importance of social change which links two or more sociological theories of hate crime pressure anomie produced by social breakdown, while the theories related to economic is seen as the root cause of hate crimes. Which created stress and frustration of the availability of limited material resources.

In the investigation of execution of forms over time, Beck and Tolnay (1995) stated, when whites felt insecure and threaten regarding their privilege, access to society and its resources, they attacked the blacks. The conflict theory of realistic group, as LeVine and Campbell (1972) claim, emphasizes on the arising of hostilities that the powers differences among groups. This has been driven from propagation of racist approach in the numerous studies after the Germany reunified. Green et al (1998) and Olzak (1989) highlighted that the important argument raised is whether interest groups and political elites created the hindrance for the perception of 'realistic' conflict. The local agitation regarding a specific group may be amplified or considered or seek by politicians and use it for their political interest. Looking for combine various features of these different approaches, the author proposed that integrating, social, psychological, and structural approaches. Koopmans (1996) and Karapin (1996) Yet, unexpectedly some researchers had drawn that both the subjective interpretation and objective conditions in creating theories particular to hate crime. Some of the researcher have assimilated political analysis of 'engineered narratives' in the context of local community propagated by groups, the routine complaints were exploited in order to propagate and gain political advantage. The applied social movement theory that the incensement of right-wing and racist violence Western Europe which combined the perceived and real grievances that may be subjective or objective structures opportunity. Green, Smith and McFalls (2001) stated that these method unable to apply in 'day-to-day hate crime', it can be occur in any

time and place apparently in any outer identifiable social movement.

Efforts to prevent hate crimes

It is important to address the incensement in hate crimes, as the results for society and individuals are numerous, and can a cause waste destruction. On the other hand, the increasing reports in hate crimes, as per federal Hate Crime Statistics Act thirty years of time and enhancements in hate crime integration in all state criminal codes virtually, the police significantly under-identified the continues hate crimes and some of the offenders of biased victimization are officially allowed in the judiciary. For instance, underreporting of hate crimes have various reasons but finally the point that significant numbers of hate crimes were not reported in the official statistics in large jurisdictions (ADL 2020). At different levels i.e. state, local and federal law enforcement agencies shall be detained the high standard of responding and reporting to hate crimes by further inclusive training and participation through community leaders and external groups to help out institutions of prioritize response to hate crimes (Pezzella & Fetzer, 2021)

It has recommended for police to improve the response to hate crime and concluded that the police department shall prioritize hate crime response timely, focus on police officers trainings, attention in high-risk neighborhoods, establishment of multi-agency task forces, increasing of police presence, responding to hate crime victims' needs, hate incidents tracking, mass media and educational institution engagement, reaching out to minority communities and monitoring hate groups (Freilich & Chermak 2013). The most important is that the accurate training and records of hate crimes by the police in order to prevent hate crimes in the community. To implement the hate crimes law against the offenders, some of the law were for the punishment of the acts i.e. protest against police just like in the Louisiana Blue Live Matter law. It is the discouragement to essential premise of laws of hate crimes which is a remedy to safeguard for the civil rights threats and violence of marginalized groups. The confinement of the masses, and enlightened movements which work to reduce the spread of carceral state, the solution is criminal justice to the

biased victimization. The effective and necessary policies to prevent groups and people are liable for threats, violence and discriminatory actions. Similarly, the noncriminal justice organizations must be more effective to address the biased incidents and hate crimes in the communities (Farrell, and Lockwood, 2002). The communities much more can be improved in various ways to support each other and accountable rather than depending on criminal justice. The efforts must be principal to reduce bias motivated victimization of the people either they are different from each other in various domains and in societal responsibilities. The racist accounts and beliefs may be revived and supported by the structure of false alternate realities which exists online on social media and news. Which having misinformation and conspiracy theories. The American society is polarized by these false reality, specifically by discouragement in trust on organizations just like media, government and the education systems. The technology played important role in feeding these crisis and hiding knowledge of the capability of social median and disinformation to weaken the democracy (Park et al, 2018).

Conclusions

There is no specific definition for hate crime although discussed in various ways by legislator, scholars, philosophers and policy makers. Some of the researchers argue that hate crime is an aggressive act while other considered it defined narrowly. In England, Scotland and wales the hate crimes defined as the aggression against marginalized groups i.e. discrimination, hate speech and micro aggression. The legal definition is based on occurrences driven by prejudice and bias, resultantly puts it in a complex situation identifying a hate incidents or a hate crime. The hate crime is widely used in UK though the precise meaning of hate crime is unclear, the ACPO and CPS is wales and England in 2007 coined a national definition for hate crime "Specifying that anyone can be a victim". The categories of hate crimes are religion or belief, disability, transgender, race and sexual orientation. The prejudice of the offenders leads to the hate crime and the victims are not to be hated. The difference between hate incidents and hate crime is critical. While hate incidents reflects bias what does not violate the law however driven by

hostility hate crime also breach the criminal law. Scholars are of the opinion that the hate crimes offenders victimize people they know. In the 1970s the concept of hate crimes coined in the United States and in the last decades given importance in the UK. Various scholars like Sociologists, Criminologists and Psychologists explored that prejudice leads to violence. Broader pattern discrimination and violence contribution to micro aggression as examined the dynamics of such offences in hate crime literature. Retaliators, defensive perpetrator, Thrill-seekers and those on mission have been identified as hate crime offenders. The main motive being a desire for dominance or rooted in prejudice, a sense of superiority, thrill to revenge and excitement drive these young males as offenders who involve in hate crimes. It is likely that these offenders have hate groups affiliation, playing a likely role in committing these offences, apart from other factors i.e. age, education, structural issues, perception of threat and attitudes. Limited literature is available in support of hate crime theories. The drivers and context knowledge is needed to realize the hate crime.

Psychological offenders are driven by emotions with prejudice as a key factor and views support them justifying violence and select the victims on the basis of social group. The violence and discrimination promoted is let by the affective disorder stereotypes as noted by Gordon Allport. Likewise, Brown agrees that offender showing authoritarian tendencies and benefits from prejudice, hence exists. The hate crime is explained though group dynamics in social psychology, where the individuals pushed by social pressure toward violence and extreme belief. Political groups and media contribute in influence hate crime towards intensifying by promoting extremist views and dramatizing events and stereotypes. Hate crimes framed a type of delinquency which showing tensions in society as per sociological perception. Relying on violence as a tool with the belief that the perpetrators, being part of extremist groups, are depending their community results in societal division. The competition for resources and social breakdown being political and economic factors also fuel hate crimes. Hate crime has a harmful impact on the society and its prevention is crucial. Unreported hate crimes needs to be highlighted, better form of law enforcement and better training is required.

Addressing policies that are effective, countering incidents that are bias-motivated, neutralizing misinformation, encouraging societal accountability and polarization in society are required for prevention of hate crime.

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